

A Comprehensive Comparative Analysis of WEKA and Tanagra for Higher Education Data Mining

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Abstract- Now in days higher education is very important for development of our country as well as for the bright future of individual one. That's why the performance of students is a big deal. Every education center is claiming that it gives quality education and best environment to its students. [1] But outcomes are not satisfying to our expectations so many researchers are trying to research in this area to get accurate result of student's accuracy. [2] With this research we will calculate the accuracy and analyze the student performance with the help of different algorithms like K-NN, Decision Tree, Random Forest and Naive Bayes and we will compare that which algorithm gives accurate result from data set and which one is best. With this research paper students and educational institutions can predict and increase self performance as required.

Keywords: Weka, Tanagra, Higher Education, Data Mining, Students Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education is an important part of our life. Without education life is not possible nowadays just because job, respect, knowledge, everything is depend on education. Higher education is required for easy life and higher standard life. Higher education is also demanded for country development and best students performance always play main role in higher education area that's why it is necessary to increase the performance of the student so with the help of data mining tools we will analyze the data and this data will be related to student performance.

In this research paper we will use two data mining tools Weka and Tanagra and we will also compare between both the tools that which tools will give more accuracy. Data mining is best technique to analyze the big data for analyzing the big data, data mining is more efficient and effective that's why we choose data mining to analyze the data.

II. DATA COLLECTION

In this research paper we have used secondary data and this secondary data collected from UCI Machine Repository. We have used Portuguese data set came from UCI Machine Learning Repository. This data actually have come from an environment where ICT technology has been used, however there are so many ICT techniques that is not used so far but we can implement those techniques to get more better results from any Data Set.

These data set already used and upload by P. Cortez and A. Silva. Using Data Mining to Predict Secondary School Student Performance. In A. Brito and J. Teixeira Eds., Proceedings of 5th Future Business Technology Conference (FUBUTEC 2008) pp. 5-12, Porto, Portugal, April, 2008, EUROIS, ISBN 978-9077381-39-7 [3].

In our data set there are overall 34 attributes which have several different capacities in these 34 attributes we have selected one attribute as our target which is actually binary attribute i.e. it has 1 & 0 only to be used. [3]

III. OBJECTIVE

1. Talk about data mining and their two important tools that are Weka and Tanagra. 2. Find the accuracy in Weka and their different techniques.
3. Find the accuracy in Tanagra and their different techniques.
4. Compare the accuracy between Weka and Tanagra.
5. Find the best data mining tools in between Weka and Tanagra as well as best their techniques also.

IV. METHODOLOGY

First of all we have collected secondary data from UCI Machine Repository. This data is related to student's performance. In the next step we have applied this data set on data mining tools like Weka and Tanagra with 10 fold cross validation. After that we have used different data models and algorithms like K-NN, Decision Tree, Random Forest and Naive Bayes and checked out that which algorithm gives the best accuracy and which tool of data mining is best about accuracy.

Figure1- Process of accuracy calculation

V. RESULT

Table1. Accuracy Comparison

USED VALIDATIONS	USED	ACCURACY(%)	
		MODELS WEKA	Tanagra
10 FOLD VALIDATION	Decision Tree	(J48) 100	90.0
	Random CROSS	Forest 98.6	NA
	K-NN	(IBK) 96.6	85.78
	NAIVE-BAYES	99.3	89.19

In this table we can see that we have used four main techniques like Decision Tree, RandomForest, K-NN and Naive Bayes in both data mining tools. And we found that the Decision Tree algorithm gave us the best results in both Weka and Tanagra data mining tools. With the help of this table we analyzed the result like this –

1. Decision Tree of weka gave us 100% accuracy but the decision tree of Tanagra gave us 90% accuracy.
2. Random Forest of Weka gave us 98.6% accuracy but in the Tanagra this algorithm is not available.
3. K-NN of Weka gave us 96.6% accuracy but the K-NN algorithm of Tanagra gave us 85.78% accuracy
4. Naive Bayes of Weka gave us 99.3% accuracy but the Naive Bayes algorithm of Tanagra gave us 89.19% accuracy.

VI. WEKA VS TANAGRA

Now we will do a comparative study between Weka and Tanagra so that we can get an idea of the best tool and their best technique.

Weka

If we talk about Weka in the table we can see that -

1. Decision Tree gave us 100% accuracy.
2. Naive Bayes gave us 99.3% accuracy.
3. Random Forest gave us 98.6% accuracy.
4. K-NN gave us 96.6% accuracy.

So we can say that best technique of Weka is a Decision Tree because it is gave us 100% accuracy from big data set. Second best technique is Naive Bayes, after that randomforest is a third number of best technique in Weka and K-NN is a very poor algorithm about accuracy compare than Decision Tree, Naive Bayes and Random Forest in Weka data mining tool.

Tanagra

If we talk about Tanagra in the table we can see that -

1. Decision Tree gave us 90% accuracy.
2. Naive Bayes gave us 89.19% accuracy.
3. K-NN gave us 85.78% accuracy.

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4. Random Forest algorithm is not available in Tanagra data mining tool.

So decision tree is the best technique of Tanagra same as Weka. Naive Bayes second best technique in Tanagra, Random Forest is not available so we are unable to compare between Weka and Tanagra Random Forest technique but again we can say that K-NN is very poor algorithm about accuracy compare than Decision Tree and Naive Bayes in Tanagra algorithm data mining tools.

So in this way we saw that the decision tree algorithm is the best in both Weka and Tanagra. But if we compare between Weka and Tanagra than we found that in every algorithm Weka is providing best accuracy then Tanagra so between Weka and Tanagra we have found Weka to be the best data mining tool.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this research paper we learned about Weka and Tanagra data mining tools. Also tried to check the accuracy of all their algorithms, at the same time we tried to achieve our objective in this research paper, in which we have been completely successful

1. In this research paper we learned about data mining as well as learned about their two important tools Weka and Tanagra.
2. We achieve the accuracy of Weka through four important techniques.
3. We achieve the accuracy of Tanagra through four important techniques.
4. We did the comparative study between Weka and Tanagra.
5. And through this comparative study we found the best data mining tools along with this we also got success in getting the best technique of those data mining tools.

FUTURE WORK:-

In future through this research students will be able to easily predict their overall performance and the data mining tools used in this research paper will prove useful for every researcher.

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International Student Conference on Next-Gen Computing:
Application of AI, Big Data, Quantum Computing, Signal
Processing and Cloud Innovations (ICNGC-2026)

International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology ISSN: 2348-4098, P-ISSN: 2395-4752

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